

README File

Modeling of pressure-induced charge transfer character in piezoluminescent pyrdiylvinylanthracene crystals

input_diabatization: example input files for diabatic calculations of dimers under ambient at high pressure

input_geom_crystals: input geometries for C1, C2, C3 polymorphs at 0 GPa

input_nci: input file for noncovalent interaction region computation using NCIPLOT programme

input_output_QE: example input and output files of Quantum ESPRESSO (QE) at 0 kbar and example in/output files of QE optimization of polymorphs at 7.92 GPa with no symmetry constraints

input_QMMM: input file for optimisation of S1 (QM/MM)

input_TDA_TDDFT: coordinates of monomer/dimer used for the TDA/TDDFT calculations and monomer in gas and THF phase

opti_crystals: optimised crystal structures at 0 and 7.92 GPa

opti_S1_QMMM: optimised geometries of S1 from QM/MM calculations